

Implementation of Hepta-band Antenna Loaded with E-shaped Slot for S/C/X-band Applications

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ABSTRACT: A small slotted MSPA with seven frequency bands and an E-shaped slot is shown in this study. The 2-by-4 rectangular patch antenna may be implemented here. The suggested setup is a strong contender for S-band, C-band, and X-band uses due to its excellent impedance matching, respectable radiation performances, and reasonable gain. When tested against state-of-the-art approaches utilising HFSS software, our design outperforms others.

KEYWORDS- Micro strip Patch antenna,
Good impedance matching and High Gain.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to review some fundamental antenna fundamentals before moving on to the Microstrip Patch Antenna (MSPA). Antennas are defined broadly as devices that convert one kind of energy into another. This study presents a comprehensive design and simulation of an E-shaped slotted MSPA, one of many varieties of MSPAs described in the literature. Research on MSP antennas has recently made significant strides. The printed circuit board is the typical medium for their production. The majority of devices that employ frequencies in the giga hertz range rely on these antennas because of their compact size. The ground, patch, substrate, and feeding portion make up a microstrip antenna. The MSP antenna has various benefits, including a compact footprint, low weight, tiny dimensions, ease of fabrication, compatibility with planar configurations, and compliance with almost all non-planar structures. It is also compatible with many MMIC designs. These MSPA's supplementary characteristics have a disproportionate impact on many studies. These might find usage in the C-band for mobile communication (apart from aeronautical mobile), the X-band for satellite applications, aviation, and space research, as well as WiMAX, medical imaging, and radiolocation. The basic dimensions, shape, sustain, and operating frequency are required to build an MSPA. However, guaranteeing the substrate in terms of size,

feasibility, and affordability is the most fundamental need. Materials ranging from 2.2 to 12 are used for MSPA.

In comparison to smaller ones, larger antennas with lower f dielectric materials achieve better profitability and higher transmission limits. A phone, tablet, computer, or game console wouldn't be complete without an antenna. In MSPA, the two conductors—the radiator and the ground plane—are encased in a dielectric substrate that has varying relative permeability and permittivity. The concept of the MSPA was first proposed in 1953, long before actual antennas were available. Various methods exist for activating MSPA equipment. Two broad categories emerge from this set of tactics: non-contacting and contacting. Coaxial probe, microstrip line, aperture coupling, and proximity coupling are some of the feeding methods used to create MSPAs. The microstrip line is the most common feeding technology due to its simplicity of manufacture and integration. The ground plane is the most crucial component of MSPA. Radiation in MSPA has developed as a result of the ground-patching effect. Utilising a variety of substrates, each with its own unique thickness, various states of patch, sizes of patch, feeding procedure, and feed position allows the reception equipment to generate radiation through irregular and rapid contact. A need for tiny multiband antennas has arisen recently due to the introduction of new measurements and smaller devices, and this is being met in various ways. Without disturbing the structure's volume, cutting holes and indents of different sizes and shapes in the ground plane or front patch are often used as part of the available data transmission capacity expansion processes. Modifying the patch width and substrate thickness is one possible approach to increasing the MSPA's Transfer speed (TS). All things considered, the problem should be enhanced with authentic upgrades while maintaining the desired emphasis or complete recurrence. Recent work by experts has shown an improved TS by the use of several outlines, such as modification of shape and patch. Because it is easy to design, requires little effort, and supports both circular and direct polarisations, the MSPA apparatus is in high demand in communication and radar systems, and it finds considerable

usage in ultra-wideband (UWB) applications. It is common practice to use a sequential stage feed for antennas in order to increase operating transfer speed and gain. In numerous seminal publications it was shown that the directivity of a conventional rectangular patch antenna is just

a function of its electrical width and length. The only practical way to increase the patch's directivity, according to the proportionality of a two-opening show, is to increase its electrical size.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Jagdish M. Rathod [3] Comparative Study of Microstrip patch antenna for wireless communication but Bandwidth is Low.

A. Kashinathan, Dr. V. Jayaraj [6] "E-Shape Microstrip Patch Antenna Design for wireless Applications" Gain is Very Low.

P. Ramaya, S. Gopalkrishnan [1] "Modified E-shaped Microstrip Patch Antenna For Wimax Applications" Return Losses are More.

Y. Rahmai [8] Wide Band E Shaped Patch Antennas for Wireless Communication Directivity is Less.

EXISTING METHOD

The proposed antenna structure is modeled on FR4 substrate (height = 1.6 mm, $r = 4.4$ and $\delta = 0.02$) with compact size of 32×32 mm², as

- 1) Antenna Design Equations The width and the length of the proposed calculated by the

detailed in Fig. 1. The proposed design consists of the ground plane and radiating patch loaded with $\lambda/4$ E-shaped slot which are jointly used as a single antenna as shown in Fig. 1. The E-shaped slot is engraved on the front patch (basic ally a radiator) of the antenna. The E-shaped structure is the elementary structure. The outline

procedure of the proposed E-shaped structure is very simple for implementation in different handheld gadgets. The detailed E-shaped slot antenna dimensions are illustrated in Table I. The presentation of this E-shaped slot adjusts the electrical current length path because of which antenna works in multiband mode with the frequencies of 3.1/4.7/6.4/7.6/8.9/10.4/11.8 GHz. The designed patch antenna is excited by microstrip feed line to achieve good impedance match at the operating bands.

following design equations

antenna can be

$$W = \frac{\lambda_0}{f_0 \sqrt{(\epsilon_r + 1)/2}}$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{(\epsilon_r + 1) + (\epsilon_r - 1) \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W}\right]^{-1/2}}{2}$$

$$L = \frac{\lambda_0}{f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} - 2\Delta L$$

$$\frac{\Delta L}{h} = 0.412 \frac{(\epsilon_{reff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.264\right)}{(\epsilon_{reff} - 0.258) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.8\right)}$$

2) Design Methodology the proposed antenna design and its detailed dimensional layouts are illustrated in Fig. 1 and Table I respectively. The antenna consists of a rectangular patch ($L1 \times W1$) in which an $\lambda/4$ E-shaped slot ($L3 \times W3 \times W7 \times L5$) is etched out. The

provided by microstrip feed line ($L6 \times W10$) using lumped port excitation. The design and the structure of the proposed antenna are intended to be used for S band (3.1 GHz), C-band (4.7/6.4/7.6 GHz) and X-band (8.9/10.4/11.8 GHz) applications.

overall impedance match is

Fig.1. Physical layout of the proposed antenna

Operate at 3.8/6.6/9.0 GHz (Fig. 3). Further modification of this slot into L-shaped slot (i.e. “Design 2”, Fig. 2) makes the antenna to operate at 3/6.4/7.3/8.5 GHz (Fig. 3). Modification of L-shaped slot into F-shaped slot (“Design 3”, Fig. 2) disturbs the current path of the radiator as a result of which antenna in “Design 3” operates at

3.6/6.5 GHz (Fig. 3). Finally, to obtain more multiple bands we lastly optimize the F-shaped slot to E-shaped slot (i.e. proposed “Design 4”, Fig. 2). This modification further affects the surface electrical current path and thus making the antenna to finally operate at 3.1/4.7/6.4/7.6/8.9/10.4/11.8 GHz.

Fig.2.Evolutionstepsoftheproposedantennastructure.

DrawbacksofExistingMethod:

- Returnlossesaremore.
- Directivityisless.

1. PROPOSEDMETHOD

Intheproposedmethod thearrayoftherectangularantennaisdesignedinorderto increasethedirectivityandreducetheradiationoftheantenna.Thedesignarchitectureofthe proposed method is given by

Fig.3.2*4Eshapedpatchantenna

In this design the specifications are:

Foreground:

- The position is 0,0,0
- X Size is 364 Size is 128. For substrate:
- The position is 64,54,1.6
- Y Size is -2 Size is 1.6 Patch size is
- The position is 34,6,1.6
- X Size is 16

- Y Size is 20

Based on the above dimensionalities the patches and rectangles are created as shown in the above figure. The substrates are filled with the FR4-Epoxy material and the radiation box is made up of vacuum. The feed is given using the lumped port.

2. RESULTS

VSWR:

RETURNLOSS:

RADIATIONPATTERN

3. COMPARISON OF RESULTS

Parameters	Eshaped patch antenna	2*4Eshaped patch antenna
Resonant frequency	3.1GHz	3.1GHz
Return loss (dB)	-33.91	-20.5
VSWR	4.1	2.4
Gain (dB)	4.5	5.52

CONCLUSION

This research presents a compact slotted MSPA loaded with E-shaped slot with seven frequency bands. Here we implemented the rectangular patch antenna of order 2 by 4. Good impedance matching, acceptable radiation performances and good gain makes the proposed configuration an attractive candidate for S-band, C-band and X-band applications. This design gets better results when compared to state of art methods.

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